

1 Sp6 and SPIB regulation in the human embryo during lineage specification to the TE.
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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 Sp6 and SPIB as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Hertveldt, V., Louryan, S., Van Reeth, T., Drèze, P., Van Vooren, P., Szpirer, J. and Szpirer, C.,
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